

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

AN INNOVATIVE MODEL FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF WOMEN'S ENTREPRENEURSHIP AS A FACTOR FOR IMPROVING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF THE BUSINESS ENVIRONMENT

Kazbekova M.

*Doctoral student of Business Administration
Almaty Management University*

Abstract

Women's entrepreneurship became a widespread aspect in modern economic conditions. There are a lot of business sectors in which women taking a niche as entrepreneur. However, in Kazakhstan women entrepreneurship is still on developing stage. There are some strong sides whereas women entrepreneurship can be more effective and can be successful. In this article we provide an analysis of current women entrepreneurship situation and develop recommendations for improvements in order to make it more competitive in economic sector.

Keywords: Women's entrepreneurship, business environment, economics of Kazakhstan, entrepreneurship in Kazakhstan, development of entrepreneurship.

Women's entrepreneurship is a "special, fulfilled project". by women view economic activities personalities, directed, in main, on self-realization social networks qualities, self-affirmation in the company, proof their abilities, using new creations new ones forms and improvements previous ones types of productions, by yourself the chosen risk, despite the difference in comparison with men of the starting positions. positions and diverse business backgrounds (education, capital, and power), but also - persisting information necessity implementations specific ones women's family and household services functions" (Hashemi, Mazdeh, Razeghi, Rahimian, 2011). On entrepreneurial activity women big influence provide specific features for each one countries factors (standards and traditions population level, structure and type economics, level development scientific, technological and industrial capacity, formal and informal institutes, etc.). As part of the study, a SWOT analysis was conducted. for business development Kazakhstan, in which the selection and evaluation of its development strategy development. They were implemented in two stages:

1. analysis internal and external environments female for business development, the information obtained determined its strengths and weaknesses (internal factors), opportunities and threats (external factors);

2. formulation possible ones strategies using SWOT matrices.

Method SWOT analysis is not only a tool diagnostics services strengths and weaknesses, opportunities and threats of the research object, but also one of the key tools used for developing strategic strategies plans. SWOT matrix promotes to your choice appropriate strategic

It also draws attention to the dynamics of the internal and external environment. Possible ones strategy options:

1. SO strategy (Maxi-Maxi): potentially the most successful strategy, which shows you what strengths you need to use in order to receive return on investment from opportunities in the external environment;

2. ST strategy (Maxi-Mini): strategy, directed information on usage internal strengths to overcome and in avoiding threats;

3. WO strategy (Mini-Maxi): strategy, showing information behind score what features external environments can to be overcome available ones weak points sides;

4. WT Strategy (Mini-Mini): a strategy that shows which weaknesses are affected necessary get rid of, to try it prevent overhanging a threat.

Among the main ones **strengths** women's entrepreneurship can be assign it to:

- Enough high level participation rates women in in business (quantity businesses, busyness, contribution in GDP);

- New generation (new wave) women entrepreneurs;

- Availability for women's purposes business associations;

- Inclusion of women from socially vulnerable groups in entrepreneurship activity.

In that time how weak points sides prevail in development female businesses in Kazakhstan:

- Representation women entrepreneurs micro and small by business;

- Specialization of women's business in the tertiary sector sector economics;

- "Double" the burden women entrepreneurs (maintenance businesses, conduction home address farms);

- Limited business statistics activities women.

In Kazakhstan are factors, which can promote development female pre-entrepreneurship in country. This such opportunities, how:

- Availability political wills for development female for business development;

- The presence of unemployed women among the working-age population and possibility their engagements in production line activity;

- Availability industrial and innovative development infrastructure;

- International integration (EAEU, etc.).

By this there are the following threats for keeping records female businesses in country:

- Gender-specific discrimination;
- New wave world class economic the crisis;
- Low entrepreneurship culture and lack of innovation cultures;
- Weak level development and inefficiency infrastructure support services female business development.

Consistent consideration of various combinations of environmental factors environments and internal ones properties female for business development of Kazakhstan allows you to justify the choice of strategic actions for its development. In accordance with the results of the constructed SWOT matrix, there can be the following areas of development of women's entrepreneurship have been implemented in Kazakhstan:

- For implementations provided by features suggested by as much as possible use available ones strong ones sides female for business development:

SO1. Export form support women entrepreneurs;

- For overcoming problems available ones the weak ones sides' female for business development suggested by usage features external environments:

WO1. Development of the high-tech sector of women's business; WO2. Development social security systems support services maternity services;

- For minimization consequences overhanging ones threats and in their avoiding suggested by usage strong ones sides' female for business development:

ST1. Development business education programs among girls;

ST2. Development infrastructure support services female for business development;

- To prevent impending threats, it is proposed to get rid of weak ones sides' women's entrepreneurship and mixing to to the minimum their influences:

WT1. Development of a system of indicators for monitoring and developing women's health business development (Vaněk, Mikoláš & Žváková, 2012).

As part of the implementation of priority strategic actions for development female for business development in Kazakhstan suggested by the following:

1. *Export form support women entrepreneurs.* For security features women's entry into new markets, particularly abroad, requires active support. support female business communities behind abroad and such national institutions development.

2. *Development high-tech sectors female businesses.* This it is not possible without increasing women's participation in the primary and secondary sector economy.

One of the ways to achieve this goal may be to expand access women's access to technical, vocational and higher education by specialties in area of interest information and communication technologies technologies, engineering, manufacturing, and construction industries, where there is more than, than two-fold gender-specific gap, what perhaps by when using it of the mechanism quotas by distribution educational services grants. Mechanism quotas can also be used in the implementation of state programs. programs. So, may it was would highlight quotas for women by financing

start-ups and high-tech businesses, as well as investment projects in realms primary and secondary sectors economy [3].

3. *Development the system social network support services motherhood.* Increase the number of kindergartens, the development of elective clubs ("extensions") in primary and secondary schools, creating children's rooms or playgrounds in business centers and other similar measures will contribute to the emergence of new ones women's businesses and growth existing ones.

4. *Development of business education among girls.* This may be the following: long-term projects courses for business development, ubiquitous enabling it in required information school card the program of the item "Entrepreneurship", training to entrepreneurship on level higher education institutions (for example, discovery the one with the same name specialties by industry). For aspiring entrepreneurs, there will be it is useful to take courses on financial improvement (basics of accounting business, investment design, business planning, etc.), legal (Business Type code of conduct, Labor code code of conduct, Tax code code of conduct and etc.), a computer program (business in on the internet, social networks networks and etc.) literacy skills.

5. *Development of infrastructure to support women's entrepreneurship.* It is necessary to ensure women's access not only to "hard" infrastructure for business development, but and to "soft" (network settings communities, usage crowdsourcing services, crowdfunding). Also to number of new ones infrastructure forms may assign it to innovative solutions camps, general fab labs, coworking space- centers, which can to be provided by state-owned companies and private ones by subjects [4].

In the development of women's entrepreneurship, the following are of great importance: ICTs (communication services tools, computer interface and modular design, digital technologies). They appear opportunities coordination services and combinations actions the big one numbers users by to the solution technically complex tasks that search for and exchange information via the Internet. The Internet. Application modern ones ICTs promotes optimizations entrepreneurial activity activities. In specific features, "virtualization" infrastructure to support women's entrepreneurship will increase the adaptability of its elements to changing factors and reduce the cost of forming and development objects a "rigid" infrastructure. Virtual infrastructure support services female for business development will provide accomplishment in virtual in space separate ones stages entrepreneurial activity activities.

6. *Development of a system of indicators for monitoring and developing women's health business development.* The main one by restriction this one researches has become lack of gender-based development indicators for business development (for example, data by to a large one for business, by volume products produced, including data in gender, age, and regional categories, industry-specific cross-section, but also in cross-section socially vulnerable people layers' population level: orphans, former employees prisoners,

housewives, young people, senior citizens, disabled people and etc.).

For quantitative assessment and monitoring of women's entrepreneurship the country needs a new system of indicators based on comparison indicators, characteristics of her entrance and exit, but also her internal the structure. As a general approach to developing a monitoring system a comparative analysis of business entities can be adopted the main ones indicators subjects for business development, headed by women, with indicators subjects for business development, headed by men, on republican and at the regional level [5].

Realization suggested ones recommendations will be promote transformation of Kazakhstan's entrepreneurial ecosystem into an efficient one mechanism socio-economic politicians, directed by on development female for business development and domestic economy in overall. Suggested set strategic ones actions requires first priority attention. Selected ones strategies not cancel it of importance promotions forward and by other directions. Received data in the course of the research, scientific results can to wear subjective personality.

References

1. Hashemi, N.F., Mazdeh, M.M., Razeghi, A., Rahimian, A. (2011) Formulating and choosing strategies using SWOT analysis and QSPM matrix: a case study of Hamadan glass company. Proceedings of the 41st International Conference on Computers & Industrial Engineering, Los Angeles, 366-371.
2. Vaněk, M., Mikoláš, M., Žváková, K. (2012) Evaluation methods of SWOT analysis. *GeoScience Engineering*, 2, 23–31.
3. Women's economic opportunity 2012. - London, New York, Geneva: Economist Intelligence Unit Limited, 2012. – 47 p.
4. The Global Gender Gap Report 2006 [Electronic resource]. URL: http://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_GenderGap_Report_2006.pdf. (Date of access: 28.11.2018).
5. The Global Gender Gap Report 2010 [Electronic resource]. URL: http://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_GenderGap_Report_2010.pdf. (Date of access: 28.11.2018).